

VUDS | VIMOS Ultra Deep Survey

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EARLY GALAXY FORMATION FROM THE VIMOS ULTRA-DEEP SURVEY

from the end of reionization to the peak in star
formation $2 < z_{\text{spec}} < 6.5$

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Outline

- Redshift $2 < z < 6$ a major epoch in galaxy assembly
- The VIMOS Ultra-Deep Survey: a spectroscopic survey of ~ 7000 galaxies
- Explore the diversity of faint galaxies properties at $2 < z < 6$
 - Spectrophotometry
 - Age, Size, stellar mass, SFR
 - Environment: mergers, proto-structures
- The evolutionary tracks of different galaxy types

SFRD from Bouwens et al. 2015

How galaxies assemble their mass ?

What regulates their SFR ?

How is the Hubble sequence forming ?

- Hierarchical picture
- Stellar mass assembly & growth may proceed from a number of physical processes:
 - Star formation from gas in DM halo
 - Star formation from Cold/Hot gas accretion
 - Merging
 - Feedback from stars, SNe, AGN
 - Regulation of gas supply, outflows, strangulation, quenching
- How and when?

➔ explore the diversity of galaxy populations

Accretion

Or

Merging

And...

VUDS: spectroscopic survey of the first phases of galaxy assembly

- 1 deg² in 3 fields (COSMOS, ECDFS, VVDS-02): mitigate cosmic variance
 - Lots of ancillary data, incl. HST and deep ground-based imaging
- 10,000 targets, T_{exp} = 14hr, VIMOS@VLT
- i_{AB} ≤ 25 and z_{phot} selected focused on 2 < z < 6
 - 1st and 2nd peak of PDF (Balmer vs. Lyman breaks) + color-selected sample (~10%)

See Le Fèvre et al. 2015

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Excellent photoz, Ilbert+ 13, 15

See Le Fèvre et al. 2015

Observations with VIMOS on the VLT

Total field $4 \times 5.5 \times 6.5$ arcmin²
Total simultaneous slits: ~600

VIMOS is in operations since 2003: one of the most productive instrument on the VLT.

After 15y service forced into retirement in 2018 ☹️☹️☹️

VUDS ~7000 spectra $z > 2$: ~3 Gyr of evolution in one glance

13 Gyr

12.6

12.2

11.6

The largest sample of UV-rest selected star-forming galaxies

A large variety of galaxy properties

- Average properties of star-forming galaxies
 - Ages and epoch of formation
 - Sizes
- Explore the population
 - Wide range of spectral properties
 - Strong line emitters $\text{Ly}\alpha$, CIII], H α ,...
 - Ultra-compact galaxies
 - Young low metallicity galaxies
 - Size and clumps in galaxies as clues to formation mechanisms
 - Environment

Epoch of galaxy formation

- Derive redshift of formation from Age and observed redshift
 - Age measurements robust at $z > 2$
- Formation redshift function (FzF):
 - Number of galaxies per unit volume formed at formation redshift z_f
- FzF: rise of 2dex from $z \sim 10$ to $z \sim 3$**
 - Similar to the rise in SFRD
 - Average SFR 8-20 Msun/year at $z \sim 5$

No particular epoch of galaxy formation

- Galaxies form at all times
- More galaxies formed when nearing the SFRD peak

Thomas et al. A&A: arXiv:1602.01841

Downsizing

- Local universe: massive galaxies seem to have formed their stars first
 - Anti-hierarchical but understood: stars form earlier in more massive galaxies but the mass assemble later
- When did this happen ?
- VUIDS: redshift of formation vs. Stellar mass at different redshifts

Results:

- Downsizing started at $z \sim 4$
 - Before $z \sim 4$: hierarchical
- Identified in simulations (GALICS, Cattaneo et al.)
 - Halo mass lower limit for star formation to be efficient $\sim 10^{11} M_{\text{Sun}}$

R. Thomas et al. submitted

What does the specific star formation rate $SSFR(z)$ tell us ?

- Bending of $SSFR(z)$ for $z > 2.5$
- Not compatible with pure accretion models
- Some other processes must be going on (merging, environment ...)

*Tasca et al. 2015, Faisst et al. 2016,
many others*

UV spectral properties

Wide range of properties

IGM Ly α CIV HeII CIII

Specific populations: CIII]-1909A emitters $2 < z < 3.8$

Ionizing field: AGN or strong early starburst ?

Classification using line ratio in progress

Fraction of emitters with $EW(CIII)] > 3 \text{ \AA} \approx 24\%$
 Not very useful as a substitute to Ly α at $z > 6$ unless the ionizing field is much stronger than at $z \sim 3$

Nakajima et al. in prep.
Le Fèvre et al. In prep.

CIII] emitters: Evidence for on-going SF quenching ?

Location of strong CIII emitters w.r.t. the main sequence at z~3

- To produce $\text{EW}(\text{CIII])} > 20 \text{ \AA}$ requires a strong ionizing field such as produced by AGN or extreme starbursts
- The strongest CIII] emitters are below the main sequence
- Their stellar populations are older

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➔ On-going quenching ? AGN+starburst?

Young forming dwarfs, low metallicity

- Redshift $z \sim 3$
- Small, $r_e \sim 0.5 \text{ kpc}$
 - Some double: mergers?
- Dwarfs: Sub- L^* , $10^{8-9} M_{\text{sun}}$
- Bright nebular emission lines
- Low gas-phase metallicity
- Forming bricks of more massive galaxies?

See Ricardo Amorin's talk

Amorin, R., et al., Nature Ast.

Galaxy size evolution $2 < z < 5$

- HST imaging (COSMOS, CANDELS) with VUDS spectroscopic redshifts
- Measure sizes
 - *Effective radius* (makes symmetry hypothesis: not good at $z > 2$)
 - *Total size* (all above a given isophote)

Results:

- Average size ~ 2.3 kpc constant w/ z
- Very large range in sizes at same redshift: 0.1 to 5 kpc radius
- Concentration gets lower with decreasing z
- Imprint of several different assembly processes ?

Total area

R_e from fit with symmetric profile (GALFIT) is plain wrong

Images of galaxies at $2 < z < 5$

Examples of the largest galaxies
Proto discs?

The same
formation process !?

Examples of the smallest galaxies
Proto spheroids?

(these galaxies have similar
stellar masses and SFR)

Discovery of Extremely Compact $2 < z < 5$ galaxies

Stellar-like on images but spectra confirm redshifts with $z > 2$

No sign of AGN

Are we witnessing the initial monolithic collapse of the progenitors of compact spheroids?

One of several formation channels?

Tasca et al., in prep.

Clumps in galaxies: clues on the galaxy formation process

- Clumps may be the result of several processes:
 - Massive star formation region
 - Violent disc instabilities (VDI)
 - Major merging
 - Minor merging
 - ...?
- Can we infer the relative contribution of each process?

Two clumps systems

≥ 3 clumps systems

Clumpy fraction: mergers and VDI

*Clump area vs.
Absolute UV magnitude*

- Besides single clump galaxies, the dominant number of clumps per galaxy is 2
 - 20 to 40% of clumpy galaxies have only 2 clumps

- The large and bright clumps are in two-clumps galaxies, too bright for VDI

➔ major mergers (~20%)

- The small and faint clumps are in multi-clumps galaxies $N_c \geq 3$

➔ violent disc instabilities

Ribeiro et al., arXiv:1611.05869

Two main modes of galaxy
mass assembly

Evolution of the merger rate

- The merger fraction remains high from $z \sim 1-2$ (MASSIV survey) to $z \sim 3-4$ (VUDS)
- $M_{\text{frac}} \sim 20\%$ in major mergers 1:4
- Integrate merger rate: L^* galaxy has \sim doubled its stellar mass from merging since $z \sim 4$
 - Mixing of stars and gas coming from different origins
- Merging: major contribution to galaxy mass assembly
 - Major impact on mass growth and mix of stellar populations with different origins
 - Impact on star formation rate may be limited (not an argument against merging)
- What was the merging rate at $z > 4$?

$z \sim 1-2$: MASSIV Lopez-Sanjuan et al. 2013

Le Fèvre et al. In prep.

SFR vs. Environment at $2 < z < 5$

Clear imprint of environment:

- galaxies with $M_{\text{star}} < 10^{10} M_{\text{sun}}$ show a higher SFR in high density regions
 - Inverted compared to $z \sim 0-0.5$
- SFR-density relation is mass-dependent
- Spectral properties are environment-dependent

*Lemaux et al.,
in prep.*

Elements for a galaxy formation scenario (post-reionization)

- The diversity of galaxy properties 0.2-2Gyr after the reionisation is striking
- There must be several different channels for forming galaxies
 - Track the progenitors of disks and spheroids
- Not simply a “Cold accretion along the cosmic web” picture with secular evolution
 - Catastrophic events: merging, quenching,...
 - Continuous processes: environment,...

≠

≠

≠

Ultra-compact

≠

major mergers

≠

disc formation

≠

massive LSB

Summary

- The epoch $2 < z < 6$ is a major epoch in galaxy formation and assembly
- Importance to probe this cosmic time with spectroscopy
 - VUDS: ~ 7000 galaxies with $z_{\text{spec}} > 2$, data releases in progress
- Very diverse galaxy properties point to several paths for galaxy formation
 - Track the progenitors of disks and spheroids observed at $z \sim 2$
 - Several galaxy formation channels and subsequent mass assembly
- Continue assembling evidence: ALMA, JWST, ...

VUDS-DR1: Public data release

~700 galaxy spectra to $z_{\text{spec}} < 6$ in CANDELS

<http://cesam.lam.fr/vuds/DR1/>

VUDS data matched to:
CANDELS-COSMOS
CANDELS-ECDFS

VUDS Identification	Alpha (J2000)	Delta (J2000)
5101244930	+10:00:47.66	+02:18:02.3

CANDELS Identification 10102
log(SFR) 1.38899 (SFR in M_{sun}/yr)
log(M^*) 9.804 (M^* in M_{sun})
Age 0.424027 (in 10^9 yr)

User friendly database - Improved statistics
Complete COSMOS release: end 2017
VVDS-XMM-LSS: early 2018

Tasca et al. 2017

Thank you

Epoch of galaxy formation

- When did galaxies observed at $2 < z < 6$ form ?
- Age measurements at $z > 2$ are quite robust (as much as mass or star-formation rate)
- Degeneracies can be lifted with
 - Age of the Universe
 - Combined fit of photometry and UV-rest spectra: promising technique for the future

Thomas et al. *A&A*, arXiv:1602.01841

Breaking the Age-metallicity degeneracy at $z > 2$